

**TOPIC: THE IMPACT OF FAMILY CONFLICT ON THE
PSYCHOLOGY OF A CHILD**

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Annotation: *This article provides extensive and detailed information about the occurrence of conflict situations in the family, the position of parents in these conflict situations, the impact on children. First of all, these are comments about the role of the family in society, that the family is a sacred place, attention to family values, a strong emphasis on the family and the relationship between the child and parents from ancient history. . In addition, the types of family disputes and the factors that cause them are explained.*

Key words: *family, conflict situations, hadiths, parents, parents' attitude towards children, marital disputes, child rearing, child psychology, cases of domestic violence.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada oiladagi nizoli vaziyatlarnong paydo bo'lishi, bu nizoli vaziyatlarda ota-ona pozitsiyasi va bolalarga ta'siri tog'risida keng va batafsil ma'lumot berilgan. Unda dastlab jamiyatda oilaning tutgan o'rni, oilaning muqaddas dargoh ekanligi, oilaviy qadryatlarga e'tibor, qadim tarixdan oilaga va aynan bola va ota-ona o'rtasidagi munosabatlarga qat'iy urg'u berilganligi haqida izohlar mavjud. Bundan tashqari oilaviy nizolar turlari va nizolarga sabab bo'luvchi omillar ham izohlab berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *oila, nizoli vaziyatlar, hadislar, ota-ona, ota-onaning farzandlarga bo'lgan munosabati, er-xotin nizolari, farzand tarbiyasi, bolalar psixologiyasi, oiladagi zo'ravonlik xolatlari.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье представлена обширная и подробная информация о возникновении конфликтных ситуаций в семье, позиции родителей в этих конфликтных ситуациях, влиянии на детей. Прежде всего, это комментарии о роли семьи в обществе, о том, что семья является священным местом, внимание к семейным ценностям, сильный акцент на семье и отношениях между ребенком и родителями из древней истории. . Кроме того, разъясняются виды семейных споров и факторы, их вызывающие.*

Ключевые слова: семья, конфликтные ситуации, хадисы, родители, отношение родителей к детям, супружеские споры, воспитание детей, детская психология, случаи семейного насилия.

Family and family relations, especially the relationship between parents and children, have been one of the most pressing issues since the earliest times of the emergence of society. As society develops, the importance of this problem continues to grow. Because it is precisely in the family environment, in the system of parent-child relations, when viewed as a connection between any other social institutions, that the achievements of humanity are most fully assimilated and passed on from generation to generation as a spiritual heritage, and this is reflected in the upbringing of children. Therefore, the prospects of a particular society, people and nation largely depend on the maturity of children raised in these relationships. For this, it is necessary to achieve a comprehensively healthy and spiritually strong internal environment in the family. Along with the achievements made today, there are also unpleasant phenomena that arise and occur in family relations: conflicts between parents and children, children leaving home, orphans living in orphanages, an increase in the number of parents who are transferred to nursing homes with their children, and serious conflicts between brothers and sisters. The fact that in some cases these conflicts lead to tragic consequences, and situations that are alien to the ethnic and traditional characteristics of the nation arise, creates the need for a special study of the characteristics of the relationship between parents and children in Uzbek families.

Issues such as family relationships, parents and children, and blood ties have played an important role not only in religious, but also in other social relations. The formation of a child born into a family as a mature person is inextricably linked to the family's education, the formation of the child's worldview, and the social status of the family. An increase in the number of children in a family, in turn, affects the level of economic support of the family, in other words, the increase in family members requires an increase in the family's financial capabilities and an increase in family income. The social function of parents is the education given to the child, and family upbringing is a key factor in the formation of the child's worldview, attitude to life, and living. Internal relations in the Uzbek family also have their own characteristics. The child's respect for parents, brothers and sisters is formed from an early age. Such issues cannot be resolved without the participation of parents, without the services of grandparents. It is also necessary to obtain their consent and blessing when organizing future life. One of the traditional features of the Uzbek family is the strong desire of children to fulfill their duty to their parents, and adults to fulfill their parental duty.

Such features are characteristic of families of almost all nationalities, but this situation is more pronounced in the Uzbek family.

The emotional connection between parents and children, between other family members, grandparents, grandchildren and close relatives in the family does not lose its influence even if the children of this family later start their own families and separate into independent families. That is, the nature of the system of interpersonal relations formed in an Uzbek family, the psychological climate in it, also significantly affects the nature of interpersonal relations in the families of future generations. Therefore, it is important to study the relationships between parents and children in Uzbek families, the characteristics of the relationships between brothers, sisters and other close relatives in the family on a scientific basis, and to determine the prospects of the Uzbek family, which has its own ethnic characteristics. In the formation of a person, such factors as the environment in the family where he is born and raised, the psychological climate in it, the relationships between family members, the child's attitude to his parents, brothers, sisters and vice versa, their attitude to the child, his lifestyle in the family, and how interpersonal relationships are organized play an important role. Therefore, in the formation of a healthy generation, it is important to study the characteristics of the impact of the above factors on the child's personality and eliminate their negative aspects. It is known that the importance of the family in the development of a child's interests, internal capabilities and abilities as a positive behavioral trait is incomparable. Especially the sensitivity of family members in their relationships leads to the transformation of any hidden talents of the child into abilities. The problem of the development of a physically and mentally healthy person who is well-rounded in all respects and his socialization is one of the urgent issues facing our state today. Because the development of any state is inextricably linked to the young generation, which is the foundation of the future, and to the healthy and strong environment in which they are brought up. In our country, which is rapidly moving towards independence, in order to ensure the healthy development and effective socialization of children, attention is paid first of all to the timely elimination of factors that negatively affect the formation of the child's personality, and to the upbringing and education of a generation that is healthy in all respects.

A number of international normative and legal documents adopted in our country provide for the protection of children's rights through law.

Recently, problems related to the influence of parents' personal characteristics on their attitude towards the child, as well as their psychophysiological characteristics, the influence of family interaction and socio-cultural factors on the child's development, its gender-related characteristics, the presence of differences in

personal characteristics, the direct influence of the family on the child's abilities, the relationship between the parent and child's relationship with the child's gender, the influence of the parent's relationship in a conflict situation on the child's behavior and the perceptions of parents and children, and the relationship between parents at different ages of the child's development, etc.

have been studied. Thus, the nature of the parental relationship affects the formation of certain personality traits in children, which, in turn, determines the possibility of successful socialization of the child in the future. Inadequate methods of family upbringing lead to the formation of neurotic, socially unacceptable personality traits in them, and difficulties in the child's adaptation to society. Modern studies on the study of child-parent relationships focus on the study of parental attitudes and the influence of parental attitudes.

The study reflects the fact that adolescents' positive and negative perceptions of family attitudes and conflicts are formed primarily on the basis of the characteristics of the relationships that are considered priority in this family, that is, depending on the principle of authoritarianism, democracy or liberalism in the system of "parent-child" relationships, as well as the direct impact of this system of relationships on the development of the child's personality.

anxiety in preschool and primary school children

develops more often in situations of internal conflict. The reasons for its occurrence are:

1. Parents' demands on their child that do not correspond to their needs and capabilities;
2. High anxiety in parents;
3. Parents' inconsistency in raising a child;
4. Making contradictory demands on the child;
5. Affectivity in parents (excessive emotionality);
6. Comparison of their own child's achievements with the successes of other children by parents;
7. Authoritarian upbringing in the family;
8. Hypersociality of parents: striving to do everything correctly, at the level of generally accepted norms and requirements.

In order to identify the causes of potential conflicts and conflicts in the family and to positively resolve the issues of their prevention, it is first of all advisable to distinguish between whom they occur. According to who participates in family conflicts, they can be divided into the following main types:

- conflicts between husband and wife;

- conflicts between mother-in-law and daughter-in-law;
- conflicts between mother-in-law and son-in-law;
- conflicts between in-laws;
- conflicts between parents and children.

Of course, this list can be continued, but for now, we will be content with the above, and the most important of the conflicts with a relatively high probability of occurring in family life, conflicts between husband and wife and conflicts between parents and children, are considered significant in the process of studying them. The behavior of a child, his upbringing is one of the most urgent problems for society in the future. Therefore, below we will consider the impact of conflicts between spouses on the psyche of a child, the causes and consequences of conflicts between parents and children.

Conflicts between spouses. In practice, when a husband and wife quarrel and decide to divorce, if there is a child in the middle, the courts resolve this matter. However, in most cases, the self-governing body of the neighborhood and activists who are members of its reconciliation commission intervene in this, and the public shows favoritism to young people who are on the verge of divorce for a trivial reason. Because

in the national mentality, leaving a child alive as an orphan is considered a great sin, therefore, there is a long-standing tradition that adults intervene in the future fate of a young family, and after studying the causes of the family conflict, a decision is reached. In cases where a family conflict seriously threatens the health, peace and coexistence of young people, primarily women and children (such as inability to forgive each other due to betrayal, regular torture of a woman due to her husband's constant alcohol consumption, domestic violence, failure to include the man's share in the family budget), the community protects the rights of women, and the mahalla itself intervenes in this matter in order to determine the fate of the woman and her children, and to provide them with social protection. Local women's activists have been paying special attention to increasing the fair activity of self-government bodies in these issues in recent years.

In psychological literature, the nature of divorces and the laws of this process are analyzed from a scientific point of view. For example, S. Krahotvil distinguishes the following stages of the divorce process:

- the stage of raising one's head: the humiliated and dissatisfied woman increases her activity and makes certain efforts to prevent the divorce from happening. However, since she does everything with anxiety and excitement, she makes many mistakes and may even do undesirable things;

- the stage of depression: the party who did not want to divorce admits that he could not control the situation, falls into a state of depression and now begins to blame himself;
- the stage of acceptance: the party who did not want to divorce now comes to terms with the current situation and comes to the conclusion that it would be better if such a marriage did not happen.

Of course, it is worth noting that in some cases, both parties consciously, by mutual agreement, do not blame each other, and such separations occur without the above-mentioned stages. And a child who sees such situations before his own eyes cannot help but receive psychological trauma. These processes have a negative impact on his psyche.

Conflicts between parents and children. The following serve as the basis for such disagreements.

1. Failure to take into account the existing difference in worldviews.
2. The fact that young people organize their free time independently, their independence in choosing friends, their independence in the field of emotions, their dressing according to fashion and current demands, their independence in choosing a profession, and their sometimes unpleasant struggle with their parents for independence in choosing a life partner.
3. Parents resorting to alcohol or compromising their honor and committing immorality.
4. The fact that some children are not taught to work and, as a result, get used to living a light-hearted life.
5. Some young people forget their duty as children.
6. Disagreements arising from the insufficient level of psychological and pedagogical knowledge of parents, etc.

As a result of the above shortcomings in the relationship between parents and children, the family loses its joy and becomes cold. What do you think about the fact that children who drink and raise their hands against their parents, and who are morally corrupt, not to mention not fulfilling their filial duties, are also ashamed of their parents? Some parents are unaware of the crises that inevitably occur in children at the ages of 1, 3, 7, and 13-14. At these age stages, new psychological attachments arise in the child's psyche. This is noticeable in their relationships with adults, including parents. Some parents, who do not realize this, think, "My child has become extremely stubborn and disobedient," and start complaining. As a result of determining their own measures against this, the parent and child cannot understand each other. In such cases, cases of separation of the child from his parents are

observed. In conclusion, studying the causes of family conflict and conducting research on it will be an effective work for the future of society. If parents approach each child individually with attention, or pay attention to the crisis periods in their child, conflict situations between children and parents will be eliminated to some extent. However, as they say, there is a second side to the coin, conflicts between husband and wife and openly shown violence cannot but have a negative impact on the child's psyche. These conditions in the child's psyche are reflected in his appearance and behavior in front of the community.

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